

Regression Analysis of Pectoralis Major Muscle Electromyography to Estimate Anterior Thoracic Cage Forces

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Abstract

Objectively measuring upper extremity weight bearing force during functional, occupational, and recreational activities that involve complex movement patterns is often not feasible. Direct *in vivo* measurement of force across the ribcage is not possible, therefore a surrogate indicator would be valuable. Muscle force is directly related to motor unit recruitment, therefore, Pectoralis Major (Pec) electromyography (EMG) may be a good indirect indicator of lateral anterior thoracic cage forces. My project aimed to predict the upper extremity weight bearing force equivalent using Pec EMG and other variables to monitor patients recovering from thoracic surgery / trauma. This retrospective study used Pec EMG and force measurements collected simultaneously at 5, 10, 20, and 30 lb intervals. Statistical analyses included Simple Linear Regression (SLR), Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR), and Random Forest Regression (RFR) modeling to predict anterior thoracic forces ($P < 0.05$). I used the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) to assess the strength of different regression models. Using SLR, the highest R-squared values were found when using all force data points and when breaking the data into old (0.343) and young (0.293) cohorts. The model was improved using MLR and adding demographic and functional variables along with EMG for both the old (0.519) and young (0.402) cohorts. Finally, RFR analysis did not improve R^2 (0.100) over the SLR, so further RFR modeling was not pursued. In conclusion, MLR using Pec EMG and resting heart rate, Timed Up and Go, and body mass index produced the most robust model, and it was improved more with the addition of handgrip strength into the old cohort model.

Introduction

Restricting upper extremity lifting, pulling, and pushing to less than 10 lb (4.5 kg) is a common precaution (Tuyl et al, 2012; Balachandran et al, 2016; Brocki et al, 2010) during post-fracture bone ossification. But, it is difficult to function independently with such significant limitations (Graham et al, 2011; Min et al, 2015). Loss of functional independence can contribute to increased time in the hospital and a greater need for assistance and rehabilitation after discharge (Min et al, 2015; Stocicea et al, 2017; Edgerton et al, 2013; Graham et al, 2011). During many upper extremity functional activities force exceeds 10 lb and often even 30 lb (Adams et al, 2006; Swanson et al, 2014). Previous research has shown that patients are not able to accurately estimate extremity weight bearing force (LaPier et al, 2019, 2021a, 2021b; Ruiz, et al., 2014). In addition, studies have demonstrated that feedback training can be useful for improving ability to modulating upper extremity force if provided objective real-time information (Raaben et al, 2018; Hustedt et al, 2012; LaPier et al, 2019, 2021a, 2021b).

Objectively measuring force placed across a bone or bone functional unit is challenging especially in the axial skeleton. During weight bearing or movement, force through an upper or lower extremity can be measured with a dynamometer during some activities. Handheld force transducers (**Figure 1**) can be used to measure force through the upper extremity. Most often, measurement of ground reaction forces (**Figure 2**) is used to measure force through the lower extremity. I previously built a force measuring walker but this can only be used during a few activities such as sit-stand transfers and ambulation with an assistive device (LaPier, 2021). Often activities have to be modified to allow placement of the force measuring instrumentation. Upper extremity closed kinematic chain activities, like pushing, are particular difficult to objectively measure. In

Figure 1. Handheld Force Dynamometer.

addition, there are many functional, occupational, and recreational activities that involve complex movement patterns during which direct force assessment is not feasible. Direct *in vivo* measurement of force across the anterior thoracic cage is not possible, therefore, the use of a surrogate indicator is needed. This would allow healthcare providers to monitor patients during a variety of activities and exercises.

Muscle force is directly related to the number of alpha-motor neurons activated during a contraction (special summation). Electromyography (EMG) is a widely used technique to quantify the number of alpha-motor neuron action potentials during a contraction via electrodes placed over (surface electrodes) or in (fine needles) the muscle (Figure 3). Measurement of EMG during a wide range of movements can be feasibly performed for a variety of muscles / muscle groups. The primary muscle attached to the anterior thoracic cage is the Pectoralis Major (Pec) and it has 3 parts (Figure 4). Contraction of this muscle may be a good indirect indicator of lateral force across the anterior thoracic cage since it is broad and superficial, has fibers that are oriented along the coronal (frontal) plane, attaches proximally to the borders of the sternum, and pulls laterally. It has 4 primary muscle actions at the shoulder: flexion, internal rotation, abduction, and horizontal adduction.

Accurately estimating force across the anterior thoracic cage would help patients recovering from injury to the ribs or sternum. Patients recovering from bone disruption due to trauma or surgery need to limit the use of their upper extremities during bone healing to minimize shear force and movement between the bone halves to protect callus formation and osteogenesis. Common patient diagnoses that require post-fracture (iatrogenic or traumatic) bone ossification include median sternotomy, anterior thoracotomies, and rib fractures / flail chest. Complications can occur when the bone halves do not heal correctly (Figure 5), including deep wound infection (osteomyelitis), bony nonunion / instability, and bone dehiscence. In addition, EMG estimation of anterior thoracic cage force would help patients titrate resumption of upper body activities and return to optimal function. Ultimately this technique may help patients transition to home safely, especially those who may not have access to follow-up services. Therefore the purpose of this study was to develop a regression model to predict the upper extremity weight bearing force equivalent using Pec EMG and other demographic and functional variables.

Figure 4. Pectoralis Major Muscle.
From: www.lecturio.com

Figure 5. Stages of Bone Osteogenesis. From: Orthobullets.com

Figure 2. Force Plate. From: DOI:10.1371/journal.pone

Figure 3. Raw EMG Data during Contraction.

Methods

This study used pooled data from a within-subjects protocol with repeated measures. Subjects ($n = 65$) were a convenience sample recruited from a university community via flyers posted around campus and sent electronically (email and text messages). Inclusion criteria were be: 1) a healthy adult between the ages of 18-40 or 60-85 years, 2) able to complete Timed Up and Go (TUG) Test in < 14 sec, and 3) able to provide informed consent. Exclusion criteria were: 1) recent (< 6 months) significant medical event (i.e. stroke, myocardial infarction), 2) pain exacerbated with UE movements / activities, and 3) any contraindication for exercise participation as outlined by the American College of Sports Medicine Guidelines for Exercise Testing (Reibe et al, 2018). This research project was reviewed and approved by the University's Institutional Review Board. On intake, information regarding subjects' demographic and baseline physiological data were obtained (see **Table 1**). The TUG Test was used as a safety screen for balance impairment (Kojima et al, 2015). Subjects were instructed to stand up from a chair, walk to and around a cone 3 meters away, and return to sitting in the chair. A time of greater than 14 sec indicates increased risk of falling and was used as an exclusion criterion (Kojima, 2015). Using continuous visual feedback (see **Figure 6**), they used constant pressure of 5 lb (2.3 kg), 10 lb (4.5 kg), 20 lb (9.1 kg), and 30 lb (13.6 kg) for 15 sec each. Both peak and average force were recorded simultaneously with Pec muscle EMG data. Subjects' functional ability was assessed using 4 standardized measurements (see **Table 1**). These evaluated function in several domains and included both performance-based and self-report functional outcomes. The outcome measures used in this study will be briefly described; all have established and acceptable reliability and validity.

Electromyography. Surface EMG was used to measure bilateral activity of the Pec muscles. Electrodes were placed 3.5 cm lateral to the anterior axillary line (Boettcher et al, 2008). An additional ground electrode was secured to the study participant's left wrist. The electrodes had dual 1x10 mm, bipolar, silver-silver chloride surfaces, an interelectrode distance of 10 mm, and on-site preamplification with a gain of 1000. They were attached to an EMG data logger (DataLOG Multisensor System MWX8, Biometrics Ltd, Newport, UK) that employed a sampling frequency of 1000 Hz and a bandwidth of 20 to 450 Hz. Surface EMG data obtained were processed and normalized. Raw EMG signals were analyzed (DataLOG Software, version 8.51, Biometrics Ltd, Newport, UK) and expressed as root-mean-square amplitude which is the square root of the average power of an EMG signal for a given period of time. A data capture window was set for each task between event markers placed during data collection. Normalization of the muscle EMG activity was done by expressing data relative to a maximal voluntary isometric contraction (MVIC) of the Pec muscle. This is a commonly accepted method to account for differences in EMG activity measurements based on muscle mass. A palm press was performed with shoulders flexed 90 degrees bilaterally with the heel of the hands together and elbows flexed 20 degrees as arms were horizontally adducted, as described by Boettcher et al (2008). Subjects held the reference MVIC for 5 sec, and the middle 3 sec were used for analysis. The mean of 3 normalization contractions was used for calculating percent MVIC.

Table 1. Variables Assessed for use in MLR.

Demographic Variables

Age
Height (Ht in)
Weight (Wt ob)
Body Mass Index (BMI kg/m²)
Heart Rate (HR bpm)
Systolic Blood Pressure (sBP mm Hg)
Diastolic Blood Pressure (dBP mm Hg)
Timed Up and Go (TUG sec)

Functional Variables

Hand Grip Strength (HG lb)
4 Squares Step Test (4SST sec)
30-sec Sit to Stand Test (30-STST reps)
RAND SF-36 Health Survey (SF-36 %)
Physical Function (Phys Func)
Energy / Fatigue (E/F)

Force. Weight bearing force through the upper extremities was measured using an instrumented walker. Force dynamometers (Jamar Smart, Performance Health, Chicago, IL) were wirelessly connected to tablets (Fire HD 10 Tablet, 1080p Full HD, Amazon, Seattle, WA) and interfaced with an application (Jamar Smart, Performance Health, Chicago, IL) that allowed continuous force data collection (see Figure 6) for up to 30 sec. The dynamometers were attached to the grip holds of a standard walker frame (Deluxe Two Button Folding Walker Drive, No. 10200-1, Drive Medical, Post Washington, NY) using platform attachments (Platform Walker/Crutch Attachment No. 10105-1, Drive Medical, Post Washington, NY) and 2.5 cm U-bolts. The front legs of the walker could also be replaced with extension legs (Tall Extension Legs, Drive Medical, Post Washington, NY) to accommodate subjects up to 200 cm tall.

Four Square Step Test (4SST). The 4SST was administered using a grid constructed with 4 PVC pipes (2.5 cm diameter) that were 91 cm long and connected in the center at 90 degree angles. The grid was secured to the floor with tape so that it would not move. Subjects were instructed to stand in square 1 facing square 2 and then were asked to step with both feet into each square as quickly as possible, first clockwise and then counterclockwise. Subjects were instructed to face forward so they stepped forward, backward, and sideways to the right and left (Dite et al, 2002). Time was recorded for 3 trials and the fastest trial was used in data analysis. The 4SST is an indicator of dynamic standing balance and gait ability (Goh et al, 2013).

30 sec Sit to Stand Test (30-STST). The 30-STST (was administered to subjects using an armless chair that was 46 (height) x 46 (width) x 46 (depth) cm. Subjects were instructed to sit in the middle of the chair, place their hands on opposite shoulders crossed at the wrist, keep feet flat on the floor, rise to a full standing position, sit back down, and repeat for 30 sec (Mehmet et al, 2019). The number of complete sit to stand and stand to sit cycles was recorded. The 30-STST is an indicator of lower body strength. Sit to stand performance has also been shown to be associated with balance, disability, and frailty (Millor et al, 2017).

Hand Grip Force (HG). Hand grip strength was measured with a digital dynamometer (GripTrack Commander; JTECH Medical, Salt Lake City, UT). For all subjects, the handle of the dynamometer was set at the middle position. Subjects stood with their arms at their sides (shoulder in neutral, elbow in extension, wrist in neutral) and 3 trials were recorded. Subjects were instructed to

Figure 6. Example Force Tracings during Each Target Weight Bearing Trial.

squeeze as hard as possible and hold for 2 sec and then relax. Subjects performed 3 trials with each hand. Rest as needed was provided between trials. The best of the 3 trials was used in data analysis. Hand grip strength is an indicator of overall upper body strength. Grip strength measured using a hand grip dynamometer is an objective measurement that has been shown to be significantly correlated with frailty and function in many patient populations including those recovering from cardiac surgery (Henry et al, 2016).

RAND 36-Item Short Form Health Survey (SF-36). In addition, the SF-36 was completed by all subjects. The SF-36 is a self-report measure of generic health-related quality of life and generates 8 subscale scores. Scores on the SF-36 range from 0 to 100 with higher values representing a more positive health state than lower values (Laucis et al, 2015). The SF-36 has been widely used in research evaluating a variety of populations including community dwelling older adults (Ramocho, et al, 2017). In addition, SF-36 scores are related to functional ability and physical activity.

Statistical Analysis. Mean EMG (of 3 trials) and peak force (over 3 trials) data were used in statistical testing. All EMG data were normalized and expressed as a percent of MVIC. In this study the dependent variable was sustained weight bearing force at 4 target intensities including 5 lb, 10 lb, 20 lb, and 30 lb. The primary independent variable was Pec EMG and the secondary independent variables included demographic and functional measurements used in the multivariable analyses. Data for the functional variables were only available for the old cohort. Descriptive statics including data normality analysis were performed. First, Simple Linear Regression (SLR) was used with sustained weight bearing force (y) & EMG (x) data. The Coefficient of Variation (R²) was used to compare the strength of different regression models. It is a statistic that indicates how much variation of a dependent variable is explained by the independent variable(s) in regression analysis.

Equation for SLR	$Y = a + bX$ <p>Y = predicted value a = regression constant b = regression coefficient</p>	$b = \frac{\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2}$ $a = \bar{X} - b\bar{Y}$
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Then, Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR) was used with force (y) and EMG (x) plus the additional variables. Stepwise Regression was performed to identify variables to include in the MLR. Multicollinearity, which is the occurrence of high intercorrelations among two or more independent variables in a multiple regression model, was checked by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for each pair of variables.

Equation for MLR	$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 \dots + b_nX_n$ <p>Y = predicted value a = regression constant b = regression coefficient</p>	$b = \frac{\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2}$ $a = \bar{X} - b\bar{Y}$
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Pearson Product Moment Correlations (r) were used to identify relationships among the selected variable. Variable Inflation Factors (VIFs) were calculated to check for multicollinearity. A summary of these steps is in **Figure 7**.

Equation for Pearson Correlation	$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$	<p>r = correlation coefficient x_i = values of the x-variable in a sample x̄ = mean of the values of the x-variable y_i = values of the y-variable in a sample ȳ = mean of the values of the y-variable</p>
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The alpha level was set at < 0.05. Statistical analyses were performed using Excel ToolPak (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA).

Figure 7. Steps used during SLR and MLR.

Finally, Random Forest (RF) modeling was used to see if it was better able to predict force from EMG plus other variables. Random Forest is a Machine Learning Algorithm that is used widely in Classification and Regression problems. It can handle data sets containing categorical or continuous variables. Random forest builds multiple parallel decision trees on different samples of a total data set. First, random records are taken from the data set (Bootstrapping). Then individual trees are constructed for each sample (Bagging). Each decision tree will generate an output (Leaf / terminal node). Lastly, final classification is determined by Majority Voting (Classification) or Averaging (Regression). For Random Forest Modeling, I used “ranger” implemented in R (Wright et al, 2017).

Results & Discussion

Descriptive statistics for the force data are shown in Table 2. Evaluation of the force data showed it had a relatively normal distribution (Figure 8) with 4 clusters corresponding the force targets (Figure 9). Kurtosis reflects the sharpness of the frequency-distribution curve peak with a perfect score equaling 0. The data had a kurtosis of -1.35 indicating a slightly platykurtic (flat) curve. Skewness is a measure of the symmetry of a

Table 2. Force Data Descriptive Statistics.

Average Force (lb)	
Mean	15.3
Standard Error	0.57
Median	12.7
Mode	5.25
Standard Deviation	9.06
Sample Variance	82.1
Kurtosis	-1.35
Skewness	0.33
Range	29.0
Minimum	3.00
Maximum	32.0
Confidence Level (95.0%)	1.12

distribution with a perfect score equaling 3. The data has a skewness of 0.33 indicating a curve slightly skewed to the left with a median higher than the mode. Based on this data, it was determined that the assumption of normality was adequately met for regression analysis.

Figure 8. Normal Probability Plot.

Figure 9. Normal Probability Plot.

Table 3 outlines a summary of SLR results including R^2 and P values for each variable. All regression analyses were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). Using log {Log} and square root {√} data transformation did not improve the model. The highest R^2 squared values were found when using EMG and all force data points plus resting and when breaking the data into old and young cohorts.

SLR Fitted Regression Model Equations:

$$\text{OLD Cohort: Force (lb)} = 7.57 + 45.38 \times (\%EMG)$$

$$\text{YOUNG Cohort: Force (lb)} = 11.55 + 47.39 \times (\%EMG)$$

Stepwise MLR (**Table 4**) was first performed to determine which demographic variables improved R^2 . This was done by calculating the changing in R^2 while sequentially adding each demographic variable. The results of this process identified 3 variables that were included in the model: Resting HR, TUG, and BMI. Next, Pearson Product Moment Correlations were calculated to determine if these 3 variables were significantly related to each other and the r values are shown in **Table 5**. I found that HR, TUG, and BMI had statistically significant correlations therefore I tested for multicollinearity. This was done by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) which quantifies how much the variance is inflated by multicollinearity for each pairing. The VIFs were all less than <5 (HR-BMI = 1.07; HR-TUG = 1.05; BMI-TUG = 1.15) indicating no regression model inflation due to multicollinearity. Stepwise MLR was repeated with the functional variables (**Table 6**) and I found R^2 was improved only with the addition of HG. Results from the MLR analysis using demographic and functional variables in addition to Pec EMG are shown in **Table 7**. The highest R^2 squared values were found when using EMG and resting HR, TUG, BMI, and HG and when breaking the data into old and young cohorts.

Table 3. Results from SLR Analyses. ($P < 0.05$)

Variables	R^2	P -Force	P -EMG
FULL Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 lb	0.198	4.6E-46	1.1E-13
FULL Cohort - 5, 10, 20 lb	0.125	2.2E-38	5.7E-07
FULL Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb	0.291	9.0E-35	3.2E-25
FULL Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb {Log}*	0.246	2.7E-67	5.5E-21
FULL Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb {√} **	0.268	8.8E-62	6.5E-23
OLD Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb	0.343	4.2E-19	1.9E-18
YOUNG Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb	0.293	5.3E-27	4.2E-14
MALE Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb	0.291	4.4E-12	2.6E-12
FEMALE Cohort - 5, 10, 20, 30 + 0 lb	0.429	6.8E-16	3.3E-22

Table 4. Demographic Predictor Variable Selection.

Predictor Variables	Change in R^2	R^2	Stepwise Addition of Variables
		0.306	EMG, Age
HR	0.017	0.323	EMG, Age, HR
	0.002	0.325	EMG, Age, HR, sBP
	0.007	0.332	EMG, Age, HR, sBP, dBP
	0.006	0.337	EMG, Age, HR, sBP, dBP, TUG
TUG	0.024	0.362	EMG, Age, HR, sBP, dBP, TUG, Ht
	0.000	0.362	EMG, Age, HR, sBP, dBP, TUG, Ht, Wt
BMI	0.020	0.382	EMG, Age, HR, sBP, dBP, TUG, Ht, Wt, BMI

MLR Fitted Regression Model Equations:

YOUNG Cohort: Force (lb) = 4.01 + 112.74 x EMG - 0.12 x HR + 0.44 x BMI

OLD Cohort: Force (lb) = -2.84 + 73.58 x EMG -0.01 x HR -0.9 x BMI + 0.16 x HG

Table 5. Pearson Correlational matrix for all Demographic Variables and VIF Scores for Highlighted Variables (HR, TUG, BMI).

	Force	EMG (%MVIC)	Age	Resting HR (bpm)	Resting sBP (mmHg)	Resting dBP (mmHg)	TUG (sec)	Height (inch)	Weight (lb)	BMI (kg/m ²)
Force	1.00									
EMG (%MVIC)	0.54	1.00								
Age	-0.01	0.20	1.00							
Resting HR (bpm)	-0.03	0.21	0.19	1.00						
Resting sBP (mmHg)	-0.01	0.18	0.40	0.29	1.00					
Resting dBP (mmHg)	-0.01	0.25	0.24	0.39	0.73	1.00				
TUG (sec)	-0.05	0.15	0.42	0.25	0.15	0.12	1.00			
Height (inch)	0.02	-0.25	-0.17	-0.11	-0.15	-0.06	-0.03	1.00		
Weight (lb)	0.01	-0.06	0.20	0.10	0.19	0.09	0.30	0.54	1.00	
BMI (kg/m ²)	0.00	0.15	0.30	0.22	0.36	0.23	0.36	0.09	0.84	1.00
<i>P</i> < 0.01 for <i>r</i> > 0.16		Colinearity VIF = 1.07		Colinearity VIF = 1.05			Colinearity VIF = 1.15			

Table 6. Functional Predictor Variable Selection.

Predictor Variables	Change in R ²	R ²	Stepwise Addition of Variables
		0.343	EMG
HG	0.114	0.457	EMG, HG
	0.008	0.466	EMG, HG, 30-STST
	0.000	0.466	EMG, HG, 30-STST, 4SST
	0.010	0.476	EMG, HG, 30-STST, 4SST, SF36-PF
	0.001	0.477	EMG, HG, 30-STST, 4SST, SF36-PF, SF36-E/F

Table 7. Results for MLR Analyses.

Variables	R ²	<i>P</i> -Force	<i>P</i> -EMG	<i>P</i> -HR	<i>P</i> -TUG	<i>P</i> -BMI
FULL Cohort – HR	0.313	0.000	0.000	0.002		
FULL Cohort – HR, TUG	0.324	0.000	0.000	0.011	0.026	<i>P</i> -BMI
FULL Cohort – HR, TUG, BMI	0.324	0.000	0.000	0.015	0.050	0.595
OLD Cohort – HR, TUG, BMI	0.421	0.001	0.000	0.060	0.326	0.714
YOUNG Cohort – HR, TUG, BMI	0.402	0.607	0.000	0.346	0.736	0.146
OLD Cohort – HR, BMI	0.417	0.001	0.000	0.039		0.442
YOUNG Cohort – HR, BMI	0.401	0.682	0.000	0.327		0.120
Variables	R ²	<i>P</i> -Force	<i>P</i> -EMG	<i>P</i> -HR	<i>P</i> -BMI	<i>P</i> -HG
OLD Cohort – HR, TUG, BMI, HG	0.519	0.693	0.000	0.897	0.590	0.000

Figure 10. RF Analysis with 2 Bins.
*Correctly Classified

Figure 11. RF Analysis with 4 Bins.
*Correctly Classified

Categorical analysis with RF had better accuracy with 2 bins (64%) than 4 bins (35%) as graphical shown in **Figure 10 and 11**, respectively. When using 2 bins with a 15 lb (6.8 kg) threshold (**Figure 12**), RF had an accuracy of 64% which was lower than the 68% accuracy obtained using MLR. The same variables (EMG, Resting HR, TUG, BMI, HG) were used in the RF model as the previous MLR. The R^2 for RF regression analysis was lower than with SLR for the old cohort, so further RF modeling was not pursued (**Figure 13**). The RF code with elements labeled can be found in the APPENDIX.

Figure 12. RF Analysis with 4 Bins. *Correctly Classified

Figure 13. Scatterplot of Test Data and Predicted Force Data for RF Regression and SLR.

Conclusions

In conclusion, Pec EMG was the strongest predictor of upper extremity weight bearing force equivalent. Breaking the data into 2 cohorts and adding HR, TUG, BMI, and HG data in the MLR improved the model’s predictive ability (see **Figures 14-17**). The most robust model was obtained with MLR with data split into young and old cohorts using EMG and additional variables with R squared of 0.52 and 0.40 for old and young cohorts, respectively. Therefore, patients’ anterior thoracic force can be reasonably estimated using Pec EMG.

Figure 14. SLR Line Plot Old Cohort.

Figure 15. SLR Line Plot Yng Cohort.

Figure 16. SLR Line Plot Old Cohort.

Figure 17. SLR Line Plot Yng Cohort.

APPENDIX. Random Forest Code

```

# Attach Packages
library(ggplot2)
library(ranger)

# Set the working directory
setwd("/Users/ansellapier/Documents/EMG Data")

#### Read in Data ####
data = read.csv("Every_Column.csv") # read in data

# Insert the median for missing values
impute.median = function(col) {
  m = median(col, na.rm = TRUE)
  col[is.na(col)] = m
  return(col)
}
df = as.data.frame(t(apply(data, MARGIN=1, FUN=impute.median)))
names(df) = names(data)

#reshape the data
m.data = data.frame("force" = c(df$FORCE.Avg.WBing.5.lb.BILAT, df$FORCE.Avg.WBing.10.lb.BILAT,
df$FORCE.Avg.WBing.20.lb.BILAT,
df$FORCE.Avg.WBing.30.lb.BILAT),
  "emg" = c(df$X.EMG.WBing.5.lb.BILAT, df$X..EMG.WBing.10.lb.BILAT,
df$X.EMG.Wbing.20.lb.BILAT, df$X.EMG.WBing.30.lb.BILAT),
  "Subject" = rep(df$Subject, 4))
m.data = merge(m.data, df[,c(1,10:53)], by="Subject")

# Check the names of the data frame
names(m.data)

# Add log transformed emg
m.data$log.emg = log(m.data$emg)

```

Data importing & reshaping

```

# Test and Training Set
smp = sample(1:nrow(m.data))
train.ind = smp[1:80]
test.ind = smp[81:108]

```

Splitting data into test set and training set

```

#### Random Forest Binned Classification ####

# Random Forest Model
m.data$binned.force = "Low"
m.data$binned.force[m.data$force>5] = "Moderate"
m.data$binned.force[m.data$force>10] = "High"
m.data$binned.force[m.data$force>20] = "Very High"
m.data$binned.force = factor(m.data$binned.force, levels=c("Low", "Moderate", "High", "Very High"))
rf.model = ranger(binned.force ~ emg + TUG....sec. + HG.Hand.Grip.Strength..lb. +
  Resting.....HR....bpm. + BMI....kg.m2.,
  data=m.data[train.ind,],
  importance = "impurity")

# Check the predictions on test set
m.data$rf.predicted = predict(rf.model, m.data)$predictions

tbl = table(m.data$rf.predicted[test.ind], m.data$binned.force[test.ind])
print(sum(tbl[1,1], tbl[2,2], tbl[3,3],tbl[4,4])/sum(tbl)*100) # print accuracy
print(tbl)

```

Random Forest classification

```

#### Random Forest Regression vs. Linear Modeling ####

# Linear Model
lm.model = lm(force ~ log.emg + TUG....sec. + HG.Hand.Grip.Strength..lb. +
  Resting.....HR....bpm. + BMI....kg.m2.,
  data=m.data[train.ind,])

```

```

# Random Forest Model
rf.model = ranger(force ~ emg + TUG....sec. + HG.Hand.Grip.Strength..lb. +
  Resting.....HR....bpm. + BMI....kg.m2.,
  data=m.data[train.ind,],
  importance = "impurity")

# Check the predictions on test set
m.data$rf.predicted = predict(rf.model, m.data)$predictions
m.data$lm.predicted = predict(lm.model, m.data)

# Calculate R^2
rf.rsquare = cor(m.data$force[test.ind], m.data$rf.predicted[test.ind])**2
print(rf.rsquare)

lm.rsquare = cor(m.data$force[test.ind], m.data$lm.predicted[test.ind])**2
print(lm.rsquare)

# Plot Observed vs. Predicted Scatterplot
ggplot() +
  geom_point(data=m.data, aes(x=force, y=rf.predicted), color="black", size=2.5) +
  geom_point(data=m.data[test.ind,], aes(x=force, y=rf.predicted, color="Random Forest"),
    size=2.5) +
  geom_point(data=m.data, aes(x=force, y=lm.predicted), color="black", size=2.5) +
  geom_point(data=m.data[test.ind,], aes(x=force, y=lm.predicted, color="Linear"), size=2.5) +
  geom_point(data=dfm.data, aes(x=force, y=predicted), size=2,
    # shape=1, color="red") +
  geom_smooth(data=m.data, aes(x=force, y=rf.predicted), method=lm) +
  geom_smooth(data=m.data, aes(x=force, y=lm.predicted), method=lm, color="orange") +
  geom_line(aes(x=5:30, y=5:30), color="red") + labs(color="Test Set Points") +
  xlab("Observed Force") + ylab("Predicted Force") +
  ggtitle("Observed vs Predicted Scatterplot - Linear and Random Forest Models") +
  theme_minimal()

```

Random Forest regression
compared to MLR with EMG, HR,
TUG, BMI, HG

```

#### Binary Classification ####
m.data$observed.bin = m.data$force > 15

# Linear Model
lm.model = lm(force ~ log.emg + TUG....sec. + HG.Hand.Grip.Strength..lb. +
  Resting.....HR....bpm. + BMI....kg.m2.,
  data=m.data[train.ind,])

# Random Forest Model
rf.model = ranger(observed.bin ~ emg + TUG....sec. + HG.Hand.Grip.Strength..lb. +
  Resting.....HR....bpm. + BMI....kg.m2.,
  data=m.data[train.ind,],
  importance = "impurity")

# Logistic Model
logit.model = glm(observed.bin ~ log.emg + TUG....sec. + HG.Hand.Grip.Strength..lb. +
  Resting.....HR....bpm. + BMI....kg.m2.,
  data=m.data[train.ind,], family = "binomial")

# Check the predictions on test set
m.data$rf.predicted = predict(rf.model, m.data)$predictions
m.data$lm.predicted = predict(lm.model, m.data)
m.data$logit.predicted = exp(predict(logit.model, m.data) ) > 0.5

# Check accuracy with bins
m.data$lm.bins = m.data$lm.predicted > 15

# Total Accuracy
lm.tbl = table(m.data$observed.bin[test.ind], m.data$lm.bins[test.ind])
print(paste0("Accuracy: ", round(sum(lm.tbl[1,1], lm.tbl[2,2])/sum(lm.tbl)*100,2),"%"))

rf.tbl = table(m.data$observed.bin[test.ind], m.data$rf.predicted[test.ind])
print(paste0("Accuracy: ", round(sum(rf.tbl[1,1], rf.tbl[2,2])/sum(rf.tbl)*100,2),"%"))

logit.tbl = table(m.data$observed.bin[test.ind], m.data$logit.predicted[test.ind])
print(paste0("Accuracy: ", round(sum(logit.tbl[1,1],
logit.tbl[2,2])/sum(logit.tbl)*100,2),"%"))

```

Binary classification

Data

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